

Earth-Scale Precursors of the Kamchatka Earthquake Revealed via Polarization Monitoring in Undersea Mediterranean Optical Fiber Links

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By tracking the polarization rotation vector in submarine optical cables carrying live traffic across the Mediterranean Sea, we unambiguously detected the signature of the recent M_w 8.8 Kamchatka earthquake in two independent optical links in the Mediterranean Sea. Moreover, distinct precursors of the earthquake were observed in multiple cables within the same region. Their distance of roughly 9,000 km from the epicenter unequivocally indicates that the earthquake preparation was governed by Earth-scale processes, whose nature remains unknown. These results demonstrate the potential of submarine optical fiber links as highly sensitive geophysical observatories, opening new perspectives for understanding earthquake dynamics and developing future early warning systems.

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1 Sensing that uses fiber-optic communication links, particu- 23
2 larly undersea systems, is an increasingly active and rapidly 24
3 growing field of research that is attracting substantial inter- 25
4 est [1–9]. A special class of techniques [2, 3, 10, 11] leverages 26
5 information already generated within application-specific in- 27
6 tegrated circuits (ASIC) of digital signal processing (DSP) in 28
7 commercial transponders [12]. Modern long-haul optical com- 29
8 munication systems employ coherent detection together with 30
9 DSP algorithms to reconstruct and compensate for the phase 31
10 and polarization changes that light undergoes during transmis- 32
11 sion [13]. These polarization changes are described by the Jones 33
12 matrix, which is sensitive to all perturbations that act on the 34
13 optical fiber along its path. Importantly, the Jones matrix can be 35
14 extracted from the DSP in coherent transponders during regular 36
15 operation with none [12] or minimal hardware modifications 37
16 without disrupting data traffic. Since no information about the 38
17 transmitted data can be inferred from the Jones matrix, its ex- 39
18 traction at the receiver poses no privacy risk (especially when 40
19 physical-layer encryption is used in addition to higher-layer 41
20 encryption). 42

21 The analysis of subsets of information derived from the Jones 43
22 matrix has demonstrated remarkable sensing capabilities for 44

detecting environmental perturbations. In particular, Ref. [2] 23
reported the detection of several earthquakes in the vicinity of 24
the Curie undersea optical cable, which connects Los Angeles, 25
California, to Valparaíso, Chile. Moreover, ultra-low-frequency 26
modulations of the hydrostatic pressure acting on the cable, 27
originating from ocean swells and semidiurnal tidal fluctuations 28
in the vicinity of the Los Angeles terminal, were revealed [3, 14]. 29
In these studies, the Jones matrix reconstructed by the receiver 30
was used to compute the output polarization corresponding to 31
a linear input polarization, and only this information was 32
processed. 33

In this work, we apply the innovative processing introduced 34
in [15] to analyze Jones matrices extracted at a sampling pe- 35
riod $T_s = 0.5$ s from five commercial coherent optical transpon- 36
ders [12]. This choice is motivated by the need to reduce the 37
volume of generated data and by the fact that it is sufficient for 38
analyzing modulations at frequencies below 1 Hz. Two transpon- 39
ders are located in Catania, Italy; one in Chania, Crete; one in 40
Rome, Italy; and one in Genova, Italy. The Catania transponders 41
operate on two segments of Sparkle's MedNautilus submarine 42
telecommunication system, connecting Catania to Haifa and Tel 43
Aviv, Israel. The Chania transponder belongs to a segment of the 44

same system connecting Athens, Greece, to Chania, Crete. The Rome and Genova transponders are part of Sparkle's BlueMed submarine system, linking Rome to Golfo Aranci, Sardinia, and Genova to Marseille, France. The transponders used in this investigation are described in [12]. Figure 1 visualizes the locations of the transponders and their corresponding links. The optical cables are lightweight, jelly-filled cables in the wet section, except for a few hundred meters near the coast. Owing to the unprecedented sensitivity of our technique, made possible by the unique features described in Sec. 2, we were able to clearly observe pre-event anomalies associated with the recent megathrust Kamchatka earthquake, at an epicentral distance of approximately 9,000 km.

As shown in Ref. [15], reciprocity in fiber propagation allows the transceivers at both ends of the link to operate as sensors. Because we target faint ultra-low-frequency signals, we select, for each bidirectional link, the terminal whose data provides the best sensing performance. Since these transponders were not originally designed for optical sensing, this pragmatic choice is appropriate in the ultra-low-frequency regime of interest.

Differences in sensitivity can arise from several factors. One is the stochastic (yet quasi-static) evolution of fiber birefringence, which generally differs between the two fibers of a bidirectional pair. Another is the stability of receiver-side components downstream of the polarization beam splitter. Inline amplifiers add amplified spontaneous emission (ASE) noise, which limits the signal-to-noise ratio (SNR) of the inferred rotation vector. In an idealized linear model with passive span loss and approximately unpolarized ASE, a polarization rotation does not depend on optical power and rotating the ASE does not change its second-order statistics; consequently, the SNR of a rotation modulation is not expected to depend strongly on the position of the perturbation within a span. Nonetheless, amplifier placement and component stability can differ between the two propagation directions, resulting in direction-dependent sensing performance, particularly at very low frequencies.

Fig. 1. Locations of the Catania, Chania, Roma, Golfo Aranci, Marseille and Genova transponders and their corresponding links.

1. METHOD

Our analysis is based on extracting, from the Jones matrix, the three-dimensional rotation vector that characterizes, for any input polarization, the change in state of polarization from transmitter to receiver [16, 17]. The evolution of polarization is described as a rotation in the three-dimensional Stokes space, which is fully characterized by its rotation vector [16].

As detailed in Ref. [15], we compensated for quasi-static input-output polarization changes using a Jones matrix obtained by a moving average of the rotation vector over either a 2-hour or 48-hour interval. This procedure effectively introduces a high-pass filter with a cutoff frequency approximately equal to one-half of the inverse of the averaging time, preventing excessive variations in the rotation vector and ensuring that a linear analysis of its fluctuations remains meaningful. We then extracted the rotation vector from the compensated Jones matrix, which encodes information on the perturbations above the cutoff frequency, and computed its spectrogram. We define a scalar, frame-invariant time-frequency representation of the rotation vector by summing the component spectrograms [15]. This quantity corresponds to the trace of the (time-varying) spectral-density matrix and is therefore independent of the chosen reference frame in Stokes space. In the stationary limit it reduces to the total component-wise spectral power (sum of the component PSDs).

Unlike previous studies [2, 3], which analyzed only the output polarization at a specific input polarization, this method fully characterizes the polarization evolution in the fiber. In addition, whereas previous spectrograms achieved a contrast of only 10 dB [2, 3, 14], our method achieved about 30 dB. Furthermore, the longer averaging times used in this work for the reference rotation vector—far exceeding the 300 s employed in earlier work—improved the low-frequency sensitivity from tens of millihertz down to tens of microhertz. Specifically, the averaging time for the Catania–Haifa, the Catania–Tel Aviv, and Rome–Golfo Aranci links was 2 hours, while for all other links it was 48 hours. The Catania–Haifa and the Catania–Tel Aviv links lie on a sediment-rich seabed, which provides strong coupling but also introduces dissipation, generating significant noise at ultra-low frequencies. This limits reliable spectral analysis below a few tenths of a millihertz and motivated the choice of a shorter averaging interval. The Roma–Golfo Aranci link also showed significant low-frequency noise. For cables immersed in water, which is more elastic and less dissipative, we used a 48-hour interval, enabling frequency resolution down to tens of microhertz in the Genova–Marseille and Athens–Chania links.

The maximum frequency of the spectrograms is 1 Hz, consistent with a sampling time of $T_s = 0.5$ s ($f_s = 2$ Hz). To reduce the maximum frequency, we decimated the samples using a low-pass Chebyshev Type I infinite impulse response (IIR) filter of order 8, effectively averaging over $N = 1\text{Hz}/f_{\text{max}}$ samples, where f_{max} is the desired maximum frequency. To reduce the maximum analyzed frequency to f_{max} , we low-pass filtered the time series with an 8th-order Chebyshev Type I IIR anti-aliasing filter and then downsampled (decimated) by a factor $N = 1\text{Hz}/f_{\text{max}}$. Spectrograms were computed using a short-time Fourier transform with a Hamming window of N_{win} samples of duration NT_s , with N_{over} samples of overlap between adjoining temporal segments. The values of N_{win} and N_{over} were chosen to achieve the desired spectral and temporal resolution. The algorithm used is fully detailed in Ref. [15]. Preliminary results on the Catania Haifa link have been reported at the Conference ECO C 2025 [18].

2. UNIQUE FEATURES OF THE SENSOR

In this section, we explain why our sensor exhibits properties that are fundamentally different from more conventional approaches. The most intuitive feature is its exceptional sensitivity at ultra-low frequencies. This sensitivity arises because polariza-

149 tion measurements are intrinsically immune to laser phase noise.
 150 At very low frequencies, sensing techniques that rely on the
 151 optical phase of even an ultrastable laser become increasingly
 152 limited by source phase noise. In contrast, polarization sensing
 153 remains effective in this regime. As shown in [3], this approach
 154 makes it possible to resolve variations in the optical path length
 155 difference between the two optical eigenpolarizations, normal-
 156 ized to the total optical path length, as small as $5 \cdot 10^{-17}$ in the
 157 millihertz frequency range.

158 A second key aspect concerns what is actually being sensed.
 159 As we will show below, our sensitivity to spatially coherent
 160 pressure fluctuations implies that the effective sensor is not the
 161 submarine cable itself, but the surrounding seawater. Seafloor
 162 motions that are coherent over horizontal scales of hundreds of
 163 kilometers generate pressure perturbations that are transmitted
 164 coherently into the water column. Through mechanical cou-
 165 pling, these pressure modulations are transferred to the cable
 166 without destroying their spatial coherence. This coherent forcing
 167 induces a differential response in the two optical eigenpolariza-
 168 tions, leading to measurable changes in the polarization rotation
 169 vector. These changes are then extracted by our signal process-
 170 ing, allowing us to observe large-scale, coherent oceanic and
 171 seafloor dynamics.

172 These features make our sensor intrinsically different from
 173 any other known sensing approach. Its output cannot be re-
 174 produced by pointwise pressure gauges deployed in seawater,
 175 because such instruments lack the sensitivity enhancement asso-
 176 ciated with spatially coherent, large-scale pressure modulations.
 177 Nor can it be reproduced by sensors located on the mainland,
 178 which do not benefit from the amplifying effect of the seawater
 179 and are additionally affected by significant anthropogenic noise.

180 Finally, the same signals cannot be recovered even by ana-
 181 lyzing noise-mitigated vibration data from gravitational-wave
 182 observatories (e.g., LIGO, Virgo, and KAGRA). Although these
 183 facilities are extraordinarily sensitive to terrestrial motion, they
 184 operate in terrestrial settings; LIGO and Virgo are largely sur-
 185 face-based, whereas KAGRA is underground, which helps mitigate
 186 some local environmental disturbances. Crucially, however,
 187 none of these observatories experiences the additional loading
 188 and pressure coupling provided by an overlying seawater col-
 189 umn. Consequently, they are not sensitive to the same class of
 190 large-scale, ocean-mediated signals detected by our system.

191 3. THE ROMA–GOLFO ARANCI LINK

192 On 29 July 2025, at 23:24:52 UTC, a M_w 8.8 megathrust earth-
 193 quake struck the Kamchatka Peninsula in Russia. It was one
 194 of the largest earthquakes ever recorded. Analysis of the po-
 195 larization perturbations at the Roma receiver of the submarine
 196 link connecting Golfo Aranci (Sardinia) with Roma (Italy) re-
 197 vealed a trace of the Kamchatka earthquake preceding the main
 198 shock. Figure 2 shows the spectrogram covering May 27 to De-
 199 cember 18, 2025. This spectrogram, like all others presented in
 200 this section, was obtained using the polarization rotation vec-
 201 tor averaged over 2 hours as a reference. A group of normal
 202 modes with frequencies slightly below 1 mHz is excited about
 203 two months before the earthquake. Their frequencies decrease
 204 as the earthquake approaches, increase later, and fade about one
 205 month later.

206 Figure 3 provides a zoomed-in view from July 9 to August
 207 17, 2025, showing that the modulation frequency never falls
 208 below ~ 0.3 – 0.5 mHz, with the exception of the vicinity of the
 209 earthquake event, where the resonance turns into a broadband

210 **Fig. 2.** Spectrogram of the rotation vector of the Jones matrix
 211 obtained from the Roma terminal of the Roma–Golfo Aranci
 212 (Sardinia) link, from May 27, 2025 to midnight on January 10,
 213 2026. The samples were decimated by a factor of $N = 200$.
 214 The reference polarization rotation vector was obtained by
 215 averaging over 2 hours, with $N_{\text{win}} = 2^9$ and $N_{\text{over}} = 2^8$.
 216 The missing data was caused by the link being out of service from
 217 August 27 through September 9.

218 **Fig. 3.** Spectrogram of the rotation vector of the Jones matrix
 219 obtained from the Roma terminal of the Roma–Golfo Aranci
 220 link, from July 9 to midnight on August 17, 2025. The samples
 221 were decimated by $N = 200$, with $N_{\text{win}} = 2^8$ and $N_{\text{over}} =$
 222 $2^8 - 1$.

223 modulation. A weaker secondary modulation is also visible at
 224 twice the frequency.

225 Insight into the origin of these spectral lines can be gained by
 226 examining the spectrogram of the rotation vector from October
 227 10 to midnight on November 18, 2025, shown in Fig. 4. This
 228 spectrogram exhibits several distinct spectral lines. The corre-
 229 sponding frequencies are more clearly identified in the power
 230 spectrum of the rotation vector computed over the same time
 231 interval and shown in Fig. 5. The fundamental period associated
 232 with these lines is approximately 2.03 hours.

233 The most likely explanation for these features is the excitation
 234 of a seiche in the Tyrrhenian basin between Italy and Sardinia. A
 seiche [19] is a standing oscillation of sea level in a semi-enclosed
 basin, characterized by a periodic redistribution of the water
 mass, with sea level rising at one end of the basin while de-

Fig. 4. Spectrogram of the rotation vector of the Jones matrix obtained from the Roma terminal of the Roma–Golfo Aranci (Sardinia) link, from October 10 to midnight on November 18, 2025. The samples were decimated by a factor of $N = 200$. The reference polarization rotation vector was obtained by averaging over 2 hours, with $N_{\text{win}} = 2^8$ and $N_{\text{over}} = 2^8 - 1$.

Fig. 6. Spectrogram of the rotation vector of the Jones matrix obtained from the Roma terminal of the Roma–Golfo Aranci (Sardinia) link, from November 18 to 14:15:10 on December 8, 2025. The samples were decimated by a factor of $N = 200$. The reference polarization rotation vector was obtained by averaging over 2 hours, with $N_{\text{win}} = 2^8$ and $N_{\text{over}} = 2^8 - 1$.

Fig. 5. Single sided power spectral density (in dB/Hz) of the rotation vector obtained from the Roma terminal of the Roma–Golfo Aranci (Sardinia) link, from October 10 to midnight on November 18, 2025. The record length is $T = 3455999.0661$ s, giving a frequency resolution $\Delta f = 1/T$. To convert the power spectral density to power per frequency bin (in dB), add $10 \log_{10}(\Delta f) = -65.3857$ dB.

Fig. 7. Spectrogram of the rotation vector of the Jones matrix obtained from the Roma terminal of the Roma–Golfo Aranci (Sardinia) link, from December 6, 2025 to midnight on January 10, 2026. The samples were decimated by a factor of $N = 200$. The reference polarization rotation vector was obtained by averaging over 2 hours, with $N_{\text{win}} = 2^8$ and $N_{\text{over}} = 2^8 - 1$.

225 creasing at the other. Such oscillations can be triggered by wind
 226 set-up or by rapid pressure changes associated with seafloor
 227 movements. A well-known example is the Adriatic (basin-wide)
 228 seiche, a ≈ 21 -h free oscillation that can contribute to Venice's
 229 *acqua alta* by constructively adding to astronomical tides and
 230 storm-surge sea-level anomalies [20]. For a one-dimensional
 231 basin of length L with reflecting boundaries, the resonance
 232 frequencies are $f_n = nc/(2L)$, where n is a positive integer and c
 233 is the phase speed of long gravity waves. In the shallow-water
 234 limit of Airy wave theory, $c = \sqrt{gh}$, with h the mean water
 235 depth. A fundamental period of $T = 2.03$ h corresponds to a
 236 basin length $L = cT/2 \approx 3.6 \times 10^5$ m when assuming $h = 1$ km,
 237 i.e. $c \approx \sqrt{gh} \approx 99$ m s $^{-1}$. This length scale is consistent with
 238 the geometry of the Tyrrhenian Sea between Italy and Sardinia
 239 and supports a seiche interpretation at the order-of-magnitude

240 level. The Tyrrhenian Sea is a semi-enclosed basin connected
 241 to adjacent basins through several openings, so the excitation
 242 of basin modes by boundary forcing is plausible. In particu-
 243 lar, Ref. [21] predicts several eigenmodes with periods in the
 244 range ~ 0.1 – 5.7 h, which overlaps the range of the observed
 245 modulation.

246 Figure 6 shows the spectrogram of the rotation vector of the
 247 Jones matrix measured at the Roma terminal of the Roma–Golfo
 248 Aranci (Sardinia) link, covering the period from November 18 to
 249 14:15:10 on December 8, 2025. The end time corresponds to the
 250 occurrence of a magnitude 7.6 earthquake in the Pacific Ocean
 251 off the coast of Aomori Prefecture, Sanriku, Japan. Interestingly,
 252 the epicenter of this event lay at approximately the same dis-
 253 tance from the Mediterranean Sea (~ 9000 km) as the Kamchatka
 254 earthquake. As shown in Fig. 6, the seiche developed an approx-
 255 imately diurnal modulation starting about 18 days before the

256 Aomori earthquake; this modulation disappeared roughly one
 257 day before the event. Following the earthquake, Fig. 7 shows
 258 that the modulation is absent, and the spectrum is characterized
 259 again by nearly stationary (constant-frequency) spectral lines.

260 This observation suggests that the pre-Kamchatka modulation,
 261 at a frequency slightly below 1 mHz, could also arise from
 262 the excitation of a seiche in a much smaller basin, such as Golfo
 263 Aranci Bay. With a characteristic width of approximately 10 km
 264 and an average depth of about 30 m, the basin between the Capo
 265 Figari promontory and Tavolara Island, in the vicinity of the
 266 Golfo Aranci terminal, has a fundamental resonance frequency
 267 of roughly 0.87 mHz. This value is consistent with the modu-
 268 lation slightly below 1 mHz observed prior to the Kamchatka
 269 event.

270 4. THE MARSEILLE-GENOVA LINK

Fig. 8. Spectrogram of the rotation vector of the Jones matrix obtained from the Genova terminal of the Marseille–Genova link, from March 1, 2025 to midnight on January 10, 2026. The samples were decimated by a factor of $N = 200$. The reference polarization vector was obtained by 48-hour averaging, with $N_{\text{win}} = 2^8$ and $N_{\text{over}} = 2^8 - 1$. The missing data were due to the link being out of service from August 27 through October 9, resulting from a cable cut. The vertical dashed line indicates the time of the Kamchatka earthquake (the zero of the time axis), and the vertical dashed line indicates the time of the 2025 Aomori earthquake.

271 Figure 8 shows the spectrogram of the rotation vector ob-
 272 tained from the submarine cable connecting Marseille (France)
 273 to Genova (Italy), covering March 1, 2025 to January 10, 2026.
 274 The reference rotation vector was obtained by averaging over
 275 48 hours, thereby enabling ultralow spectral resolution down to
 276 tens of microhertz. A resonance around 1 mHz appears about
 277 four months (120 days) before the earthquake, decreases slightly
 278 in frequency a few days afterward, and disappears at the end
 279 of October (approx 120 days after the event). Compared to the
 280 spectrogram of the Roma–Golfo Aranci link, the earthquake pro-
 281 duces a smoother effect on the resonance and, as illustrated in
 282 Fig. 9, the daily modulation is also less pronounced. By analogy
 283 with the Roma–Golfo Aranci link, this resonance can also be
 284 attributed to the excitation of a seiche along the cable path.

285 A striking feature appears in the low-frequency range (0–0.2
 286 mHz) shown in Fig. 10. Several months before the earthquake,
 287 strong activity was observed, characterized by impulsive varia-

Fig. 9. Spectrogram of the rotation vector of the Jones matrix obtained from the Genova terminal of the Marseille–Genova link as in Fig. 8, limited to the interval from July 9 to midnight on August 17, 2025. The samples were decimated by $N = 200$, with $N_{\text{win}} = 2^8$ and $N_{\text{over}} = 2^8 - 1$.

Fig. 10. Ultra-low-frequency portion of the spectrogram in Fig. 8. The samples were decimated by $N = 5000$, with $N_{\text{win}} = 2^8$ and $N_{\text{over}} = 2^8 - 1$. Similarly, the vertical dashed line indicates the time of the Kamchatka earthquake (the zero of the time axis), the vertical dashed line indicates the time of the 2025 Aomori earthquake.

288 tions in the rotation vector, as indicated by the vertical lines in
 289 the spectrogram. A comparison with Fig. 8 suggests that this
 290 activity is related to solid Earth tides, as the density of these
 291 vertical lines intensifies during periods of spring tide. This im-
 292 pulsive behavior is also apparent in the time-domain traces of
 293 the rotation-vector components (extracted without spectral fil-
 294 tering) and of its squared magnitude, as shown in Fig. 11.

295 Unlike the Athens–Chania link, the solid-Earth tidal effect
 296 is so strong here that it manifests itself as impulsive variations
 297 of the polarization rotation vector. These impulses produce the
 298 vertical lines observed in the spectrograms, drive the polariza-
 299 tion response beyond the linear regime, and therefore prevent
 300 a rigorous spectral analysis. Nevertheless, a notable feature
 301 is that the influence of distant tides abruptly disappears after
 302 the earthquake. This is evident in Fig. 10, which shows that,
 303 post-event up to 110 days, the noise in this ultra-low-frequency
 304 region is greatly reduced, allowing spectral lines with diurnal

and semidiurnal periodicity to become visible at $f_1 \simeq 11.57 \mu\text{Hz}$ and $f_2 \simeq 23.15 \mu\text{Hz}$. Impulsive noise reappears 110 days after the Kamchatka earthquake, again 20 days before the Aomori earthquake, and then disappears once more afterwards.

The white region in the spectrograms corresponds to missing data resulting from an interruption in cable operations from August 31 to October 9, 2025, caused by a cable cut. Peaks observed in Fig. 10 and 11 immediately before the interruption and after service resumption, which were caused by transients associated with the shutdown and restart.

5. THE CATANIA–HAIFA LINK

The links connecting Catania to Haifa and Catania to Tel Aviv are the only ones in which a clear signature of the Rayleigh waves generated by the Kamchatka earthquake could be observed, both in the spectrogram of the rotation vector and in the temporal traces of its components.

Fig. 11. Traces of the three components of the rotation vector $\vec{\varphi}(t)$ and its modulus obtained from the Genova terminal of the Marseille–Genova link. Red dashed and dash-dotted lines indicate the time of the Kamchatka and the Aomori earthquakes, respectively.

In Fig. 12, we show the spectrogram of the rotation vector obtained from the Catania terminal of the Catania–Haifa link. The time axis extends from half a day before to half a day after the earthquake, with the zero point set at the time of the earthquake. Between 30 and 70 mHz, a clear wave-train (highlighted by the red oval) is visible as a narrow ellipse with a slight positive slope, indicating that lower frequencies arrive earlier than higher frequencies and suggesting a minor anomalous dispersion characteristic of the Rayleigh waves. The time axis thus spans one full day centered on the earthquake, with zero corresponding to the event time.

Figure 13 shows the traces (in radians) of the three components of the rotation vector filtered in the band between 30 and 70 mHz and, in the subplot at the bottom right, the square modulus of the filtered rotation vector. The time span covers three hours after the earthquake, clearly showing the event signature. The red dashed vertical lines mark the arrival of the perturbation, which occurred about 45 minutes after the earthquake. This arrival time is consistent with a train of Rayleigh waves. These are surface seismic waves that propagate along the boundary of a solid (or between two solids), analogous to gravity waves on the surface of a fluid [22]. Because Rayleigh waves have a transverse component, they couple to seawater pressure, enabling the cable to detect resulting pressure changes. Assuming

Fig. 12. Spectrogram of the rotation vector of the Jones matrix obtained from the Catania terminal of the Catania–Haifa link. The time axis spans 24 hours centered on the earthquake. The reference polarization rotation vector was computed by averaging over a 2-hour window. The spectrogram was generated by decimating the samples by $N = 10$, with $N_{\text{win}} = 2^9$ and $N_{\text{over}} = 2^9 - 1$. It is shown for the frequency range between 20 and 80 mHz, where the Rayleigh pulse—highlighted by a red oval—is clearly visible.

Fig. 13. Traces of the three components of the rotation vector $\vec{\varphi}(t)$ and its modulus obtained from the Catania terminal of the Catania–Haifa link, filtered in the band between 30 to 70 mHz, displayed up to 3 hours after the earthquake. The origin of the time axis is again at the earthquake occurrence time. The red dashed vertical lines denote 45 minutes after the earthquake.

a distance of 9,000 km from the epicenter, the estimated speed of the Rayleigh wave train is $v_R = 3.3 \text{ km/s}$, a realistic value for waves traveling in the deep crust or mantle. Given the spectral width $\Delta f \simeq (70 - 30) \text{ mHz}$, the estimated coherence length of the source is $D \simeq v_R / \Delta f \simeq 83 \text{ km}$. Similar features are observed in the Catania–Tel Aviv link, as shown in Figs. 14 and 15, which display the spectrogram and the corresponding temporal traces of the rotation vector extracted from the Catania receiver. The other spectral signatures observed in these spectrograms are likely due to seabed tremors, which are more pronounced in this cable because of more efficient coupling to the seabed, resulting from the cable being covered by Nile Delta sediments.

We now analyze the spectrograms of the rotation vector extracted from the Catania–Haifa link focusing on the Catania

Fig. 14. Spectrogram of the rotation vector of the Jones matrix obtained from the Catania terminal of the Catania–Tel Aviv link. The time axis spans 24 hours centered on the earthquake. The reference polarization rotation vector was computed by averaging over a 2-hour window. The spectrogram was generated by decimating the samples by $N = 10$, with $N_{\text{win}} = 2^9$ and $N_{\text{over}} = 2^9 - 1$. It is shown between 20 and 80 mHz, where the Rayleigh pulse—highlighted by a red oval—is clearly visible.

Fig. 15. Traces of the three components of the rotation vector $\vec{\varphi}(t)$ and its modulus obtained from the Catania terminal of the Catania–Tel Aviv link, filtered in the band between 30 to 70 mHz, displayed up to 3 hours after the earthquake. The origin of the time axis corresponds to the time of earthquake occurrence. The red dashed lines indicate 45 minutes after the event.

Fig. 16. Spectrogram of the rotation vector of the Jones matrix obtained from the Catania terminal of the Catania–Haifa link, from April 10, 2025 to midnight on January 10, 2026. The origin of the time axis is at the earthquake occurrence time. The samples were decimated by $N = 200$, with $N_{\text{win}} = 2^9$ and $N_{\text{over}} = 2^8$.

Fig. 17. Spectrogram obtained by decimating by $N = 100$ the samples of the rotation vector of the Jones matrix extracted by the Catania terminal of the Catania–Haifa link, from July 1st to midnight on August 26, 2025. The origin of the time axis is, as before, at the time of earthquake occurrence. The reference polarization rotation vector was obtained by averaging over 2 hours, with $N_{\text{win}} = 2^8$ and $N_{\text{over}} = 2^8 - 1$.

359 receiver. Figure 16 shows the spectrogram of the rotation vector
 360 of the Jones matrix obtained from the Catania terminal of the
 361 Catania–Haifa link, from April 10, 2025 to midnight on January
 362 10, 2026. All spectrograms use the rotation vector averaged over
 363 2 hours as a reference (see Ref. [15]). Figure 17 presents the
 364 spectrogram of Fig. 16 restricted to the interval July 1 to August
 365 26, 2025. Besides straight lines at frequencies multiple of 4.5,
 366 5 and 9 mHz (artifacts of the phase recovery algorithm of the
 367 receiver's DSP), the striking feature is the appearance, about 20
 368 days before the earthquake, of multiple resonances at $\sim 2, 4, 6,$
 369 and 8 mHz, which disappear a few days after the event.

370 Figure 18 zooms in on the low-frequency portion of Fig. 17.
 371 In addition to a nearly diurnal modulation, the resonance fre-
 372 quencies exhibit a minimum approximately at the time of the

373 earthquake. This is especially evident in the resonance at ~ 4
 374 mHz, highlighted with a dashed line and oval in Fig. 18. This
 375 strongly suggests that the resonances were generated by pro-
 376 cesses that were preparing for the earthquake, observed 9,000
 377 km away.

378 We defer the interpretation of these spectral features to the
 379 following section, where we discuss similar features observed in
 380 the spectrograms of the Athens–Chania link. Before concluding
 381 this section, however, we present in Fig. 19 the power spectrum
 382 of the rotation vector obtained using, as a reference, a rotation
 383 vector averaged over 48 hours. This choice effectively introduces
 384 a lower low-frequency cutoff than that obtained using a 2-hour
 385 averaging window. In this spectrum, a sequence of peaks ap-
 386 pears at frequencies that are integer multiples of $f_1 = 14.0107$
 387 mHz, corresponding to a period of 19.8 hours. These peaks can

Fig. 18. Zoom of the low-frequency portion of the spectrogram in Fig. 17, obtained by decimating the samples by $N = 200$, using $N_{\text{win}} = 2^8$ and $N_{\text{over}} = 2^8 - 1$.

388 be attributed to pressure fluctuations induced by inertial cur-
 389 rents. Such currents arise from a balance between the Coriolis
 390 force and the centripetal acceleration, in a dynamical regime
 391 characterized by a Rossby number of order unity, where inertial
 392 effects are comparable to rotational effects and pressure-gradient
 393 forces are of secondary importance [23]. The period of inertial
 394 currents is given by $T = 2\pi/[2\Omega \sin(\phi)]$ where Ω is the Earth's
 395 angular rotation rate and ϕ is the latitude. Using the latitude
 396 of Catania, $\phi = 37.5^\circ$ we obtain $T \simeq 19.7$ hours, in good agree-
 397 ment with the observed 19.82-hour period of the fundamental
 398 spectral peak. The peaks at multiples of the Coriolis frequency
 399 arise because a fundamentally single-frequency inertial oscillation
 400 becomes distorted by various nonlinear processes. Note
 401 also that the power spectrum of the rotation vector exhibits over
 402 many decades a decay proportional to $1/f^2$, characteristic of the
 403 well-known low-frequency random-walk dynamics of seawater
 404 pressure [24]. This behavior provides further evidence that the
 405 cable is sensitive to fluctuations in seawater pressure.

406 6. THE ATHENS–CHANIA LINK

407 We observe similar features on the optical link connecting Athens
 408 (Greece) to Chania (Crete). The seafloor in this region contains
 409 fewer sediments than that of the Catania–Haifa link, allowing a
 410 richer spectrum of phenomena to be observed, as the coupling
 411 with seawater pressure modulations is less dissipative. This
 412 circumstance enabled us to use the polarization rotation vector
 413 averaged over 48 hours as a reference, rather than the 2-hour
 414 average used for the Catania–Haifa link. As shown in Fig. 20,
 415 we detect the same resonances observed on the Haifa–Catania
 416 link, including three resonance lines appearing more than a
 417 month later. A comparison with the IRIS earthquake catalog
 418 for the Kamchatka region [25] (Fig. 21a) indicates that these
 419 resonances coincide with two major aftershocks of magnitude
 420 7.3 and 7.7, which occurred on 13 September and 18 September,
 421 respectively, and represent the most energetic subsequent events
 422 in the area. Figure 21 also reports (b) the magnitude–frequency
 423 histogram, consistent with Gutenberg–Richter scaling [26], and
 424 (c) the spatial distribution of epicenters over the 100-day window
 425 before and after the main event. Notably, seismicity in the region
 426 was nearly quiescent until approximately ten days prior to the
 427 M_w 8.8 mainshock.

Fig. 19. Single sided power spectral density (in dB/Hz) of the rotation vector of the Jones matrix obtained from the Catania terminal of the Catania–Haifa link, from April 10, 2025 to midnight on January 10, 2026, obtained by using as reference a rotation vector averaged over 48 hours. The record length is $T = 22982397.7587$ s, giving a frequency resolution $\Delta f = 1/T$. To convert the power spectral density to power per frequency bin (in dB), add $10 \log_{10}(\Delta f) = -73.614$ dB.

Fig. 20. Spectrogram of the rotation vector of the Jones matrix obtained from the Chania terminal of the Athens–Chania link, from April 18 to 6 a.m. on November 13, 2025. The origin of the time axis corresponds to the time of earthquake occurrence. The reference polarization rotation vector was obtained by averaging over 48 hours. The samples were decimated by $N = 200$, with $N_{\text{win}} = 2^8$ and $N_{\text{over}} = 2^8 - 1$.

428 The spectrogram in Fig. 20 also shows an additional pulsed
 429 train of oscillations centered around $f \simeq 0.5$ mHz, close to the
 430 resonance ${}_0S_3$ of the Earth's spheroidal mode $f_0 = 0.46848$ mHz
 431 [27–29]. This resonance is more evident in the spectrogram of
 432 Fig. 22, where we increased the frequency resolution (at the
 433 expense of temporal resolution) by using $N_{\text{win}} = 2^{10}$ instead of
 434 $N_{\text{win}} = 2^8$ as in Fig. 20. Figure 23 presents the low-frequency
 435 portion of the spectrogram, showing that the resonance begins
 436 about 60 days before the earthquake, intensifies a few days
 437 before, and fades away after approximately 70 days.

438 A zoomed-in view of the spectrogram, covering one month
 439 before and one month after the earthquake, is shown in Fig. 24.
 440 The temporal traces of the three components of the rotation

Fig. 21. (a) Earthquake magnitudes greater than 4 recorded in 100 days before and after the main earthquake in the Kamchatka region (46° – 55° N, 150° – 162° E). (b) histogram of the earthquake magnitude and (c) location of the epicenters in the same period. The shadow regions in (a) refer to the time range of the resonances in Fig. 20

Fig. 22. Same as Fig. 20, but with $N_{\text{win}} = 2^{10}$ and $N_{\text{over}} = 2^9$, increasing frequency resolution.

Fig. 23. Low-frequency portion of the spectrogram in Fig. 22. The samples were decimated by $N = 1000$, with $N_{\text{win}} = 2^8$ and $N_{\text{over}} = 2^8 - 1$.

of this excitation.

The analysis of the power spectrum of the rotation vector shown in Fig. 26 provides further insight into the nature of this excitation. The power spectrum exhibits two main peaks at $11.5045 \mu\text{Hz}$ and $23.1196 \mu\text{Hz}$, corresponding to periods of 24.245 and 12.015 hours, respectively. The first peak is about 7 dB higher in power (i.e., a factor of ~ 5) than the second. In addition, the spectrum exhibits a broad peak near 0.5 mHz. A zoomed-in view of the spectrum around the broad peak is shown in Fig. 27.

The observed spectral comb is consistent with an impulsive excitation of the ${}_0S_3$ mode, whose frequency $f_0 = 0.46848 \text{ mHz}$ is indicated by a red dashed line [29]. The spacing between the comb lines, $\Delta f = 11.564 \mu\text{Hz}$, corresponds to a pulse-repetition period of $T = 1/\Delta f \approx 24.02$ hours.

For a more quantitative interpretation, we model the oscillations with a linearly damped harmonic oscillator

$$\ddot{x}(t) + \gamma\dot{x}(t) + \omega_0^2 x(t) = F(t), \quad (1)$$

where $F(t)$ is a periodic train of impulses of strength F_0 with daily period $T_d = 24 \text{ h}$, representing the effect of the diurnal component of the Earth tides

$$F(t) = F_0 \sum_{n=-\infty}^{\infty} \delta(t - nT_d). \quad (2)$$

The response to a single impulse at $t = 0$, i.e. $F(t) = F_0\delta(t)$, is

$$x_0(t) = \frac{F_0}{\omega_d} e^{-\gamma t/2} \sin(\omega_d t) \Theta(t), \quad (3)$$

where

$$\omega_d = \omega_0 \sqrt{1 - \frac{\gamma^2}{4\omega_0^2}}, \quad (4)$$

and $\Theta(t)$ is the Heaviside step function. Because the system is linear time-invariant, the response to an impulse train is the superposition of time-shifted impulse responses $x(t) = \sum_{n=-\infty}^{\infty} x_0(t - nT_d)$. A periodic sequence of pulses generates a comb of spectral lines, whose envelope is proportional to

$$|\tilde{x}(\omega)|^2 = \frac{F_0^2}{(\omega^2 - \omega_0^2)^2 + \gamma^2\omega^2}. \quad (5)$$

vector, filtered in the 0.4–0.6 mHz band, presented in Fig. 25 together with their moduli, clearly reveal the impulsive nature

469 For $\gamma < \sqrt{2}\omega_0$, the envelope reaches its maximum at

$$\omega_{\max} = \omega_0 \sqrt{1 - \frac{\gamma^2}{2\omega_0^2}}. \quad (6)$$

470 For weak damping, the 3 dB bandwidth of $|\tilde{x}(\omega)|^2$ is $\Delta f_{3\text{dB}} \simeq$
471 $\gamma/(2\pi)$, implying

$$f_{\max} = f_0 \sqrt{1 - \frac{\Delta f_{3\text{dB}}^2}{2f_0^2}}. \quad (7)$$

472 From Fig. 26, the 3 dB (half-power) spectral width in the
473 power spectrum is $\Delta f_{3\text{dB}} \simeq \gamma/(2\pi) \approx 0.1$ mHz, corresponding
474 to a damping rate $\gamma = 2\pi\Delta f_{3\text{dB}} \approx 6.3 \times 10^{-4} \text{ s}^{-1}$. Accord-
475 ingly, the envelope of the spectral comb produced by periodic
476 excitation of the ${}_0S_3$ mode should peak at $f_{\max} \simeq 0.463$ mHz,
477 close to the peak observed in Fig. 27. The amplitude envel-
478 ope decays as $\exp(-\gamma t/2)$, implying an amplitude decay time
479 $\tau_A = 2/\gamma \simeq 3.18 \times 10^3 \text{ s}$ (~ 53 min), while the correspond-
480 ing power (energy) decay time is $\tau_P = 1/\gamma \simeq 1.59 \times 10^3 \text{ s}$.
481 The width observed in the time-domain traces appears how-
482 ever two or three times longer, suggesting that the pulses are
483 not transform-limited. The decay time of the pulses is how-
484 ever much shorter than that usually associated with the ${}_0S_3$
485 mode. Indeed, assuming exponential ringdown $e^{-\gamma t/2}$ and
486 $Q = \omega/\gamma$ for normal modes, the amplitude e-folding time is
487 $\tau_{\text{amp}} = 2/\gamma = Q/(\pi f)$; with $f_0 \approx 468.55 \mu\text{Hz}$ and $Q_0 \approx 445$,
488 $\tau_{\text{amp}} \approx 3.5$ days [30]. The much shorter decay time suggests
489 that we are not observing the intrinsic damping of the Earth
490 normal mode, but rather the ringdown of water-column oscilla-
491 tions (and the associated pressure modulation) triggered by an
492 impulsive seafloor excitation near the normal-mode frequency.
493 We discuss this point further in Section 7.

494 **Fig. 24.** Spectrogram of the rotation vector of the Jones matrix
495 obtained from the Chania terminal of the Athens–Chania link,
496 from 30 days before to 30 days after the earthquake. The origin
497 of the time axis corresponds to the time of the earthquake
498 occurrence. The samples were decimated by $N = 500$, with
499 $N_{\text{win}} = 2^8$ and $N_{\text{over}} = 2^8 - 1$. The reference polarization
500 rotation vector was obtained by averaging over 48 hours.

494 The spectrogram in Fig. 28 shows that this excitation is part
495 of a broadband resonance extending up to ~ 4 mHz, which grad-
496 ually fades. These resonances follow the same pattern as the
497 Rayleigh oscillations observed on the Catania–Haifa link. As

501 **Fig. 25.** Traces of the three components of the rotation vector
502 $\vec{\varphi}(t)$ and its modulus obtained from the Chania terminal of the
503 Athens–Chania link from July 19 to August 18, 2025, filtered in
504 the 0.35–0.65 mHz band, showing the impulsive nature of the
505 excitation.

506 **Fig. 26.** Single-sided power spectral density (dB/Hz) of the
507 rotation vector from 18 April to 13 November 2025. The record
508 length is $T = 18079910.4779 \text{ s}$, giving a frequency resolution
509 $\Delta f = 1/T$. To convert the power spectral density to power per
510 frequency bin (in dB), add $10 \log_{10}(\Delta f) = -72.572 \text{ dB}$.

506 shown in Fig. 29, the excitations are significantly weaker and
507 less broadband two months after the earthquake.

508 The occurrence of resonances with the same temporal evolu-
509 tion and frequencies on both the Athens–Chania and Catania–
510 Haifa links, each with a landing point in Chania, suggests that
511 the spectral lines observed near integer multiples of ~ 2 mHz on
512 both links are associated with the Chania landfall. Consequently,
513 a more plausible interpretation of these lines—compared with
514 the Rayleigh-wave resonance proposed in [18]—is the excitation
515 of a local seiche [31] in the semi-enclosed coastal environment at
516 the cable landfall, namely the cove at Nea Chora Beach (Chania).
517 The presence of spectral lines at both even and odd harmonics
518 indicates that the basin response at these periods is not restricted
519 to a simple quarter-wave resonance (odd-only), but likely in-
520 volves closed-basin-like modes and/or coupled eigenmodes of
521 adjacent basins.

522 Seiche activity in semi-enclosed basins in the Chania area has
523 been documented in the literature. In particular, the Venetian
524 harbor of Chania—located ~ 1.5 km from the beach manhole
525 where both cables land—exhibits a well-defined resonant period

Fig. 27. Zoom of the power spectral density in Fig. 26 around 0.5 mHz. The red dashed line marks the frequency $f_0 = 0.46848$ mHz of the Earth's spheroidal mode ${}_0S_3$ [29]. The frequency separation between two peaks of the spectral comb that are 13 teeth (orders) apart is $f_{n+13} - f_n = 0.532082 - 0.38175$ mHz, which corresponds to an average spacing of $\Delta f = 11.564$ μ Hz. Notice that $f_n/\Delta f = 33.012$, i.e., very close to an integer. This implies that the phase advance between successive pulses is approximately $2\pi \times 33$, so the pulse phase is highly periodic.

Fig. 28. Spectrogram of the rotation vector of the Jones matrix obtained from the Chania terminal of the Athens-Chania link, from 20 July to midnight on 9 August 2025. The origin of the time axis corresponds to the time of the earthquake occurrence. The samples were decimated by $N = 100$, with $N_{\text{win}} = 2^8$ and $N_{\text{over}} = 2^8 - 1$.

of approximately 480 s, corresponding to a fundamental frequency $f_1 \simeq 2.1$ mHz with higher harmonics at $f_n = nf_1$ [32, 33]. A high- Q harbor resonance of this kind is expected to couple to the surrounding coastal ocean through the open boundary and to radiate long, barotropic waves at the resonant frequencies into the nearshore region. Given the long wavelengths associated with these periods (of order several kilometers), a cable located a few kilometers from the source remains within the near field of the radiated signal, so that the fundamental and its harmonics can be detected with little frequency distortion. In this framework, oscillatory water-level and pressure signals generated by the coupled harbor-cove system, when excited by broadband

Fig. 29. Spectrogram of the rotation vector of the Jones matrix obtained from the Chania terminal of the Athens-Chania link, from 19 October to midnight on 8 November 2025. The samples were decimated by $N = 100$, with parameters identical to Fig. 28.

long-period forcing, can propagate into the adjacent bay and be recorded by the submarine cables, naturally accounting for the observed spectral lines near integer multiples of ~ 2 mHz.

Taking all these observations together, we interpret the results as follows. Solid Earth tides can excite stress concentrations in the Kamchatka region [34, 35], which in turn trigger Earth's normal modes. The spheroidal mode ${}_0S_3$ is spectrally well separated from neighboring modes, and is therefore preferentially excited. Because this excitation is not sustained in time due to dissipation, it manifests as a train of exponentially decaying pulses. In contrast, modes that are closer in frequency—and further broadened by mode splitting—form a quasi-continuous spectral band that appears as vertical features in spectrograms. Oscillations of higher-order spheroidal modes are equivalent to Rayleigh-wave trains; when their spectral content overlaps a nearby basin resonance, the response can be amplified and sustained, producing temporally continuous spectral lines.

For the Venetian harbor, the excitation mechanism is inertial coupling to seafloor acceleration, which produces a pressure perturbation in the overlying water column, $\delta p(t) = \rho h \ddot{x}(t)$, where ρ is the water density and h is the basin depth ($h \sim 3\text{--}5$ m for the Venetian harbor). The observed daily modulation of the resonance arises from local tides, which modulate the effective depth h on diurnal timescales ($\Delta h \sim 0.5$ m in the Venetian harbor) and thereby shift the seiche resonance frequency. Because the harbor is shallow, the resulting pressure variations remain small in amplitude, helping to keep the polarization-rotation vector modulation within its approximately linear regime and enabling an interpretable analysis.

This perspective also suggests that the spikes observed on other cables (for example, the Genova–Marseille link) may arise from the same seafloor acceleration that generates the train of pulses near the ${}_0S_3$ frequency, but amplified by the substantially greater local water depth h . Whereas the Athens–Chania link reaches a maximum depth of about 500 m, the Genova–Marseille cable exceeds 2500 m, producing correspondingly larger hydrostatic pressure perturbations. Moreover, the longer span of the Genova–Marseille link increases the path length over which these pressure variations influence the optical signal. The resulting pressure perturbation, $\delta p(t) = \rho h \ddot{x}(t)$, may therefore exceed

the linear-response regime of the polarization-rotation vector, with the corresponding wideband modulation producing the vertical lines observed in the spectrograms.

Finally, the longer-timescale variability observed in the Athens–Chania link (and in the Roma–Golfo Aranci link)—including a pronounced minimum occurring near the time of the earthquake—may reflect spatially selective coupling between the seafloor forcing and basin eigenmodes. In this picture, the spatial structure of the forcing preferentially excites particular resonances; if the forcing geometry evolves over longer timescales, the dominant excited resonance, and thus the observed modulation, may shift accordingly.

The effects of solid tides originating from Kamchatka should precede those of local tides in the Mediterranean Sea by about nine hours. Moreover, distant tides cannot affect the Mediterranean region at frequencies below the lowest Earth-mode frequency (~ 0.4 mHz). Consequently, below this threshold, only local tidal effects should be observable. To evaluate the hypoth-

Fig. 30. Normalized cross-correlation of the temporal traces of the amplitude of the rotation vector filtered in the 0.4–0.6 mHz band (distant solid tides) and those low-pass filtered below 0.4 mHz (local tides).

Fig. 31. Normalized cross-correlation of the temporal traces of the amplitude of the rotation vector filtered in the 0.4–0.6 mHz band and those high-pass filtered above 1 mHz, both dominated by distant solid tides.

Kamchatka region, we therefore computed the normalized cross-correlation between the temporal traces of the amplitude of the rotation vector filtered in the 0.4–0.6 mHz band and those low-pass filtered below 0.4 mHz. The results (Fig. 30) indicate that the low-pass filtered traces, dominated by local tides, lag about three hours behind the band-pass filtered traces, influenced by distant solid tides. This lag is less than the expected nine-hour delay, possibly due to the damping tails of the normal-mode oscillations, which shift the center of mass of the modulation and reduce the apparent lag in the cross-correlation.

Figure 28 shows that oscillations of the resonances at 2 mHz and 4 mHz are in phase with the impulsive excitations around 0.4 mHz. The fact that these impulsive excitations precede local tides by several hours strongly indicates the nonlocal origin of the resonances at 2 mHz and 4 mHz, reinforcing the hypothesis that they are related to the Kamchatka event.

We also computed the normalized cross-correlation between the amplitude traces filtered in the 0.4–0.6 mHz band and those high-pass filtered above 1 mHz. The plot in Fig. 31 shows that the cross-correlation reaches its maximum at zero time lag, supporting the hypothesis that both signals are dominated by distant tides.

7. COMPARISON WITH A LAND-BASED SEISMOGRAPH

To compare the undersea-cable observations with those from a conventional land-based instrument, we retrieved waveform data for station GIGS from the public database [36]. Station GIGS is a broadband seismic station installed in the underground laboratories of the Gran Sasso National Laboratory (LNGS), L’Aquila, Italy [37]. The resulting spectra are shown in Fig. 32. In brief, the time series were multistage downsampled from 100 Hz to 0.01 Hz using four successive factor-10 polyphase FIR resampling steps, and the power spectral density (PSD) was then estimated in the 0.2–1.0 mHz band using Welch’s method with 2-day Hamming windows and 50% overlap. The solid black curve reports the spectrum estimated from the 10-day interval following the earthquake, the red dot-dashed curve from the 10-day interval preceding the event, and the blue dotted curve from a 10-day reference interval more than six months after the earthquake. For clarity, the pre-event and reference spectra are scaled by a factor of 100. Following the earthquake, the excitation of several spheroidal modes is clearly observed, in some cases also exhibiting Coriolis splitting that lifts the m degeneracy. By contrast, no *continuous* excitation of Earth’s normal modes is apparent either before the event or during the reference period recorded more than half a year after the earthquake.

To enable a fair comparison with the seismograph data, we analyzed the Athens–Chania rotation vector with a similar method after removing a slowly varying reference obtained as a 48-hour running average. For each compensated component, we estimated the PSD in the 0.2–1.0 mHz band using Welch’s method with 1-day Hamming windows and 50% overlap. We then formed a scalar spectral measure for the compensated rotation vector by summing the PSDs of the three components, i.e.,

$$P_{\text{tot}}(f) = P_x(f) + P_y(f) + P_z(f). \quad (8)$$

Finally, we removed the dominant low-frequency trend consistent with a $1/f^2$ dependence by fitting and subtracting a linear slope in log–log coordinates. Specifically, we modeled $\log P_{\text{tot}}(f)$ as a linear function of $\log f$ over the analyzed band,

$$\log P_{\text{tot}}(f) \approx a \log f + b, \quad (9)$$

esis that the observed resonance is excited by solid tides in the

Fig. 32. Spectrum of the vertical ground motion recorded by a broadband seismometer at the Gran Sasso National Laboratory (LNGS), L'Aquila, Italy. The solid black curve was computed from a 10-day record spanning 29-Jul-2025 23:24:52 to 08-Aug-2025 23:24:52 (post-event). The red dot-dashed curve was computed from a 10-day record spanning 22-Jul-2025 23:24:52 to 29-Jul-2025 23:24:52 (pre-event). The blue dotted curve was computed from a 10-day record spanning 01-Feb-2026 00:00:00 to 11-Feb-2026 00:00:00 (reference period). For clarity, the red dot-dashed and blue dotted spectra are multiplied by 100. Vertical red dashed lines mark the frequencies of the spheroidal Earth's normal modes (in increasing order) ${}_0S_2$, ${}_2S_1$, ${}_0S_3$, ${}_0S_4$, ${}_1S_2$, ${}_0S_0$, ${}_0S_5$, and the three nearly degenerate modes ${}_1S_3$, ${}_3S_1$, and ${}_2S_2$. Vertical blue dotted lines denote the toroidal modes ${}_0T_2$, ${}_0T_3$, ${}_0T_4$, and ${}_0T_5$.

Fig. 33. Spectrum of the Athens–Chania rotation vector after compensation by subtraction of a 48-hour running average. The displayed spectrum is obtained by summing the PSDs of the three compensated components, $P_{\text{tot}}(f) = P_x(f) + P_y(f) + P_z(f)$. As in Fig. 32, the solid black curve corresponds to a post-event 10-day record, the red dot-dashed curve to a pre-event 10-day record, and the blue dotted curve to a 10-day reference period spanning 01-Feb-2026 00:00:00 to 11-Feb-2026 00:00:00. Vertical red dashed and blue dotted lines indicate the same normal-mode frequencies as in Fig. 32.

with a fitted exponent a close to -2 ; the fitted values are $a = -2.135$ (pre-event), $a = -1.947$ (post-event), and $a = -2.099$ (reference), indicating only modest departures from the ideal

$1/f^2$ trend. The detrended spectrum was obtained by subtracting the fitted line in log space (equivalently, dividing $P_{\text{tot}}(f)$ by the fitted power-law background in linear space) and then transforming back to the original scale.

The choice of a 1-day Hamming window (rather than the 2-day window used for Fig. 32) is motivated by the need to mitigate the spectral modulation associated with the one-day periodicity of the impulsive excitation.

The results are shown in Fig. 33. A broadband enhancement in the vicinity of the ${}_0S_3$ frequency is visible both in the 10-day interval preceding and in the 10-day interval following the earthquake. In contrast, it is absent in the reference period, which was acquired more than half a year later.

Overall, these observations suggest that the cables are primarily sensitive to *impulsive*, large-scale coherent seafloor motions, whose associated acceleration induces abrupt variations in seawater pressure. By contrast, they are largely insensitive to *quasi-static* (adiabatic) seafloor deformation, which is not associated with significant acceleration and therefore does not substantially perturb the water-column pressure. These results highlight the complementarity between distributed cable-based sensing and point-like measurements by land-based seismographs. The absence of continuous normal-mode excitation before the earthquake in the land-based record is consistent with the hypothesis proposed in Sec. 6 that the pulse train observed in the polarization-rotation vector near the ${}_0S_3$ frequency on the Athens–Chania link reflects a ringdown of the water column triggered by an impulsive seafloor excitation at (or near) the normal-mode frequency, rather than a long-lasting transient excitation of the normal mode itself.

8. DISCUSSION

The observations consistently suggest that solid Earth tides and their interaction with the Earth's normal modes are the primary drivers of the observed phenomena. Several lines of evidence—including the sensitivity of the system to seawater pressure and the observation of seiches in the Tyrrhenian Sea with the Roma–Golfo Aranci cable—indicate that seiches play a significant role, due to their ability to amplify small, spatially coherent modulations resonantly. The forces driving the excitation of these seiches are unlikely to originate from local dynamics; rather, they appear to reflect a global, Earth-scale process, as evidenced by their temporal behavior, which shows a clear influence from the Kamchatka earthquake, more than 9,000 km away.

A possible explanation for the seiche excitation is the constructive interference of body waves emitted by the seismic source in the Kamchatka region, which are detected at the cable location after a single reflection from mantle discontinuities. The spatial profile of this excitation may vary daily as the position of the emitter changes, thereby exciting different resonant paths for the seiches. When the emitter's motion is approximately orthogonal to the source–receiver direction, the variation in distance is minimal, producing only a slight effect on the spatial profile of the excitation. This scenario could account for the small modulation amplitude of the spectral line observed in the Genova–Marseille spectrograms.

The different responses of the cables to continuous excitations may reflect their selective sensitivity to the spatial profile of the excitation. Submarine cables exhibit exceptional sensitivity because they can detect coherent modulations over large spatial scales, indicating a strong dependence on the excitation's spatial characteristics. Each cable may therefore act as a spatial filter,

710 preferentially coupling to modes whose spatial profile matches
711 its own.

712 9. CONCLUSION

713 In summary, we detected signals preceding the M_w 8.8 megathrust
714 earthquake that struck the Kamchatka Peninsula on
715 29 July 2025 using multiple submarine cables in the Mediter-
716 ranean Sea. These results were enabled by an innovative pro-
717 cessing approach applied to the Jones matrix extracted from
718 coherent receivers during normal cable operation [15], yielding
719 unprecedented sensitivity to coherent seawater-pressure fluctu-
720 ations over large spatial scales associated with seafloor seismic
721 activity. This level of sensitivity indicates that the Mediterranean
722 basin can function as a large-scale seismic sensor, with the wa-
723 ter column responding to solid-Earth forcing and the resulting
724 pressure field being detected by the cables.

725 The large distance between the epicenter and the observa-
726 tion points, about one quarter of Earth's circumference, strongly
727 suggests that earthquake preparation involved Earth-scale pro-
728 cesses of yet unknown origin. We speculate that the excitation
729 of Earth's normal modes or the constructive interference of body
730 waves may be revealed through the amplifying mechanism of
731 seiches. This challenges existing models of Earth's oscillatory dy-
732 namics and indicates that solid tides may play a far more active
733 role in global geophysics than previously recognized, paving
734 the way to a better understanding of the earthquake dynamics.

735 The ability of submarine cables to detect coherent seawater
736 pressure modulations at continental scales introduces a new
737 class of geophysical observatories that could enable real-time
738 monitoring of Earth's normal modes and their coupling to tidal
739 forces. Future work should investigate whether these findings
740 imply persistent energy transfer mechanisms within the mantle
741 and assess their implications for seismic hazard modeling and
742 Earth system science. It is interesting to note that, although the
743 volume of telemetry data to be processed with this technique
744 is non-negligible, the use of the polarization rotation vector for
745 sensing allows the sampling time to be limited to values on the
746 order of half a second (which is the sampling time used in this
747 study). This significantly reduces the amount of telemetry data
748 that must be stored and processed. For example, more than
749 seven months of state of polarization data are contained in a
750 single 1.6 GB file. Looking ahead, techniques based on artificial
751 intelligence will be crucial for the automated detection and pro-
752 cessing of phenomena of interest. Furthermore, telemetry from
753 multiple links could be post-processed both locally and centrally
754 to improve our understanding of ongoing activity in the Earth's
755 crust.

756 Beyond advancing fundamental understanding, this tech-
757 nique opens a new observational window into earthquake
758 physics and holds promise for developing next-generation early
759 warning systems.

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766 and commercialized by Infinera (now Nokia).

767 **Data availability.** Data underlying the results presented in this paper
768 will be available in a public repository of Project Zenodo (Ref. [38]).

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